

Manufacturing-induced Cogging Torque in Segmented Stator Permanent-magnet Machines with respect to Steel Punching

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There are applications like electric power-assisted steering system in which strict requirements on the cogging torque of the machine should be fulfilled. Numerous techniques and methods are introduced in order to minimize the inherent cogging torque of the machine, but manufacturing tolerances and imperfections still can cause extra cogging torque. In this paper, the impact of punching on the manufacturing-induced cogging torque of segmented permanent-magnet synchronous machines is investigated. The punching model is implemented by modifying the BH curve of the steel as a function of distance from the cut edges. The parameters of the new BH curve are identified by means of standard Epstein frame measurements using steel strips with different widths. Then, the punching model is incorporated into the finite element model of a 10-pole 12-tooth segmented stator machine designed for power steering application. It is observed that deviation among the magnetic properties of the teeth caused by punching can introduce extra low-order harmonics in the cogging torque of the machine. The amplitude of the new orders can be comparable or even much bigger than the inherent orders, where not only the magnitude of deviation but also the arrangement of teeth with given punching parameters play a role.

Index Terms—Cogging torque, Manufacturing imperfections, Permanent-magnet Synchronous Machines, Power Steering, Punching.

I. INTRODUCTION

OWING to high power density, permanent-magnet synchronous machines (PMSMs) are widely used in cars in different applications ranging from auxiliary systems to powertrain [1]–[4]. In automotive-related applications, there are strict requirements on the torque ripple in general and cogging torque in particular. First of all, smooth output torque is required in order to limit vibration and acoustic noise, which is a key requirement in cars [5]. Secondly, in some functions precise position control at low torque is required, and therefore small torque ripple or cogging torque can easily deteriorate the drive performance [6]. Take, for instance, electric power-assisted steering system in cars. When the car is driven at high speeds in a highway, the driver normally rotates the steer just by quite small angles. In this case, the cogging torque of the PMSM used in the system can adversely affect the drive performance. It can not only impair the position control but also lead to unpleasant steering feel.

Numerous techniques are introduced in the literature in order to minimize the inherent cogging torque of the machine, for example, stator or rotor skewing, magnet surface shaping, dummy slots, rotor surface shaping, to name but a few [7], [8]. However, the manufacturing process can introduce extra cogging torque into machine [9]–[11]. This new cogging torque that originates from imperfections related to manufacturing can be even bigger than the inherent cogging torque of the machine, particularly in low cogging torque applications. The manufacturing-related imperfections can be classified into three categories, namely, geometrical tolerances, assembly tolerances, and variation of material properties.

Geometrical tolerances relate to various dimensions of the motor, like tooth dimension, magnet dimensions, stator and rotor yoke, and many others [12]. Depending on the cutting tools and methods, these dimensions can vary according to geometrical tolerances, which can introduce asymmetry among stator teeth and rotor poles. Assembly tolerance can be related to the stator and rotor. On the rotor side, the magnets can be displaced in circumferential or even axial direction [13]. Moreover, rotor eccentricity in the form of static, dynamic, or mixed also can occur, which depends on the bearing placement tolerances [14]. On the stator side the displacement of the teeth in segmented PMSMs in the form of radial displacement, tilting, or imperfect connection between teeth of segmented stators can occur [15].

Material properties variation can be caused by permanent magnet (PMs) and electrical steels properties. In the case of PMs, the magnet remanence, permeability, or magnetization direction can slightly vary among different poles [16]. Similarly the magnetic properties of the electrical steel can vary among different teeth of the stator [17]. For example, while cutting the teeth of segmented PMSMs by punching or laser-cutting, electrical steel degradation due to mechanical or thermal residual stress can vary among different teeth, which can introduce asymmetry in the stator [18].

As a general rule, stator-related asymmetries result in cogging torque orders which are multiples of number of poles (p), while rotor-related ones lead to orders being multiples of number of stator slots (N_s), with the exception of the eccentricity. Static eccentricity introduces p -multiple orders, while dynamic eccentricity generates N_s -multiple orders.

Many papers have identified the impact of geometrical and manufacturing tolerances as well as material property vari-

ations on the performance of PMSM in general and cogging torque in particular [19], [20]. Furthermore, the degradation of the machine performance in terms of iron losses and torque due to the punching has been measured and reported [21], [22]. However, the effect of punching on the cogging torque, particularly manufacturing-induced term, is less-known. This issue is more relevant in segmented stator PMSMs, as the teeth of stator are punched separately, as opposed to a single-body stator, and therefore some variation among teeth is inevitable.

In this paper, the manufacturing-induced cogging torque of a 10-pole, 12-tooth PMSM designed for electric power-assisted steering is investigated. The steel degradation due to the punching is studied by measuring the magnetic properties of the steel strips with different widths and modeled by representing the BH curve of material as a function of the distance from the cut edges. Then, the position-dependent BH curve is incorporated into the FE model, and the impact of material deterioration on the cogging torque is simulated.

In the next section, the machine under study and its FE model will be set forward. Then, in section III, the model of punching and its identification will be introduced briefly. In the section IV, the incorporation of the punching model into magnetostatic FE will be discussed, and its effect on the cogging torque of the machine will be discussed in section V. In section VI, the effect of teeth arrangement on the cogging torque will be discussed. Finally, the paper will be concluded in section VII.

II. PMSM UNDER STUDY

The PMSM has 10 poles and 12 teeth with tooth-wound winding. The rotor has surface-mounted bread-loaf-shaped magnets. Surface-shaped magnets are used in order to minimize the inherent cogging torque of the machine. The cross-section of the machine is shown in Fig. 1 and its relevant parameters are reported in Table I.

The machine is modeled using finite element (FE) method by open-source software ONELAB [23]. The FE mesh for one tooth of the stator and one pole of the rotor is shown in Fig. 2. In order to avoid extra harmonics in the cogging torque due to numerical errors, the one-pole and one-teeth symmetry of the mesh should be respected. Otherwise, even with completely symmetric stator and rotor some unexpected harmonics, however with small amplitude, in the cogging torque content can be observed.

The cogging torque of the machine with symmetric and asymmetric stator over one period (considering stator asymmetry, the periodicity of cogging torque increase from 30 to 180 electrical degree) is shown in Fig. 3 (a). Moreover, the corresponding harmonic contents are shown in Fig. 3 (b). The cogging torque of the symmetric stator referred to as inherent cogging torque is composed of 60-multiple orders ($lcm(10, 12)$), while with the asymmetric stator, there are extra 10-multiple orders (order means number of periods per one mechanical rotation). It should be noted that stator-induced cogging torque affects also inherent cogging torque. However, as the order of basic harmonic of the inherent cogging torque is six times bigger than the basic order of stator-induced cogging torque, the influence is expected to be negligible.

Fig. 1. Cross-section of the 10-pole 12-tooth PMSM under study

Fig. 2. FE mesh of (a) stator tooth and (b) rotor pole

III. PUNCHING MODEL

This section is mainly adapted from the paper recently published by the authors [20] and it is included for the sake of completeness. The magnetic steel under study is M330-50A. In order to model the effect of punching on the magnetic properties (MgPs) of the steel, the BH curve and iron losses are measured using four types of strips (see Fig. 4). The total width of each strip is 30 mm. However, it can be composed of thinner sub-strips with widths 6, 7.5, 10, or 15 mm. The tests are conducted using five various combinations of the strips by means of standard Epstein frame. The type and number of strips in each test is reported in Table II. According to the IEC 60404-2 standard, there are 8 strips in total in each test, half of which are cut in rolling direction and half in transverse direction. The measured BH curves and iron losses are shown in Fig. 5 and 6 as solid lines, respectively [20].

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE PMSM UNDER STUDY

number of poles	10
number of teeth	12
magnet remnant field	1.35T
stack length	50 mm
outer dia. of stator	85 mm
tooth height	10.5 mm
tooth width	8.1 mm

Fig. 3. The cogging torque of the machine with symmetric and asymmetric stator

In order to consider the effect of the punching on the MgPs of the steel, the permeability of the non-degraded steel is modified as follows [20]:

$$\mu(H, x) = \mu_{n\text{-deg}}(H) \left(1 - \frac{2}{\pi} \mu_p \exp\left(\frac{-x}{a_\mu}\right) \left(\arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_1}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_2}\right) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

where x is distance from the nearest cut edge in m, and H field intensity in A/m. $\mu_{n\text{-deg}}$ is the permeability of the non-degraded material in H/m, assumed to be equal to the permeability of standard 30mm-wide strips. The four parameters μ_p , H_1 , H_2 , and a_μ need to be identified.

With the Epstein frame test, the average value of the flux

Fig. 4. The 30mm-wide strips used in Epstein test with 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 sub-strips with width 30, 15, 10, 7.5, 6 mm, respectively (from up to down) [20]

TABLE II
NUMBER AND WIDTH OF STRIPS USED IN EPSTEIN FRAME TEST (THE FIRST AND SECOND NUMBERS IN PARENTHESES SHOW THE NUMBER AND WIDTH OF THE SUB-STRIPS, RESPECTIVELY) [20]

test	# and width of strips	# of cut edges
1	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (3×10mm)	40
2	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (4×7.5mm)	48
3	4 × (2×15mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	56
4	4 × (3×10mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	64
5	4 × (4×7.5mm) + 4 × (5×6mm)	72

density and therefore average permeability in the strips can be measured. Assuming that H in (1) is independent of position and constant, the reduction in average permeability of the strip due to punching is calculated by integrating (1) over the width of strip as:

$$\Delta\mu(H) = \frac{2}{\pi} \mu_p \left(\arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_1}\right) - \arctan\left(\frac{H}{H_2}\right) \right) \left(\frac{1 - \exp\left(\frac{-2w}{a_\mu}\right)}{\frac{-2w}{a_\mu}} \right) \quad (2)$$

where w is the length of the strips.

The iron losses density based on IEM-modified formula [24] is computed as [20]:

$$P(B, x) = k_{h0} \left(1 + k_p \exp\left(\frac{-x}{a_p}\right) \right) f B^{\alpha_0} + k_{e0} (1 + x_{10} B^{x_{20}}) f^2 B^2 \quad (3)$$

with

$$B = \mu(H, x) H \quad (4)$$

where P is iron losses in W/kg, f is the frequency of magnetic field variation in Hz, B magnetic flux density in T. k_{h0} , α_0 , k_{e0} , x_{10} , and x_{20} are loss parameters calculated for strips with negligible cutting effect, i.e. 30mm-wide strips. k_p and a_p are for representing the effect of punching on iron losses.

The term $(1 + x_{10} B^{x_{20}})$ in (3) is for considering the increase of eddy-current loss due to saturation [24]. It is assumed that cutting does not affect eddy current losses. Hence, the punching effect is just considered in the hysteresis loss term. Again, since the measured iron losses are averaged over the strip, the average iron losses need to be calculated as:

$$P_{\text{avg}}(H) = \frac{2}{w} \int_0^{\frac{w}{2}} P(x) dx \quad (5)$$

Obviously, (2) and (3) are valid for a single sub-strip with given width; and, therefore, they should be calculated for all strips in each test separately and added up proportionally for considering their cumulative effect [20].

In order to identify the unknown parameters in (2) and (5), the fitting problem is defined as a least-square optimization [25]. It should be mentioned that the identification is defined as a single problem, as opposed to identifying the BH curve and iron losses parameters separately, because the BH curve degradation changes the magnetic field distribution and consequently increases the iron losses indirectly. The optimization problem is solved using *fmincon* function in MATLAB.

Fig. 5. Iron losses at 50 Hz for tests 1 to 5 reported in Table II; solid lines are measured losses and the squares show fitted values [20]

Fig. 6. BH curves at 50 Hz for tests 1 to 5 reported in Table II; solid lines are measured and the markers show fitted values [20]

The fitted iron losses BH curve alongside the measured ones are shown in Fig. 5 and 6 with markers, respectively. Measurements were available just at single frequency 50 Hz. The computed coefficients in (1) and (3) are reported in Tables III and IV. In order to achieve better agreement between the fitted curves and measured values, the coefficients in Table IV can be calculated as a function of flux density. However, for the sake of simplicity regarding to statistical study in Section V, it is preferred to work with single-value coefficients.

Fig. 7. The distance and permeability maps as a function of the distance to the central node marked with a red circle; (a) distance map and (b) permeability map with discrete model, (c) distance map and (d) permeability map with continuous model

TABLE III
IRON LOSS PARAMETERS DEFINED IN (3) [20]

k_{h0}	α_0	k_{e0}	x_{10}	x_{20}
0.027	1.76	5.3e-6	1.85	2.88

TABLE IV
PUNCHING COEFFICIENTS DEFINED IN (1) AND (3) [20]

μ_p (-)	H_1 (A/m)	H_2 (A/m)	a_μ (mm)	k_p	a_p (mm)
2.5	35.9	128.1	2	0.67	1.74

IV. FE IMPLEMENTATION OF PUNCHING MODEL

Considering punching effect, the permeability of steel is not only a function of field intensity but also the nearest distance from the cut edges. In order to incorporate the position-dependent BH curve into FE model, two different approaches can be adopted. In the first approach, the distance of the centroid of each triangular mesh from the nearest cut edge is used for determining the permeability of the steel. It means that the permeability over each single element is constant; or it is represented as a element-wise constant function. As an example, the map of the distance from the central node, which is marked by a red circle, is shown in Fig. 7 (a). The corresponding permeability with imposed flux density 1T in all elements is shown in 7 (b).

Alternatively, the nearest distance of each node from the cut edges can be stored and used for determining the permeability of the steel. In this case, the distance over a single element surface has linear profile. Consequently, the permeability will be a step-wise linear function. Again, in Fig 7 (c), the map of distance from the central node is shown. Furthermore, the corresponding permeability with imposed flux density 1T is shown in Fig. 7 (d). As it can be seen in this case the permeability changes continuously over the elements.

With sufficiently fine elements, both approaches should result in the same result. In this paper, the latter approach is adopted because of ease of implementation with ONELAB.

In Fig. 8, the flux density distribution in a single tooth with and without punching effect is shown. The average flux density 1 T is imposed by applying proper boundary conditions on the two sides of the tooth trunk. Ignoring punching effect, the flux density distribution in the middle of the tooth is almost uniform and equal to 1 T. However, with punching effect, there

Fig. 8. Single tooth model with imposed average flux density 1 T in the tooth trunk; (a) without punching effect, (b) with punching effect

Fig. 9. The magnetic properties in the cut edge (dashed lines) and far away from the cut edge (solid line) obtained based on (1); (a) BH curve (b) relative permeability

is flux concentration in the middle of the tooth. Because of the steel degradation, the flux density is lower in the region near to the cut edges compared to the middle of the tooth trunk; it increases from around 0.7 T in the cut edges to 1.2 T in the middle of the tooth. Similar effect can be seen in the yoke as well.

V. PUNCHING EFFECT ON THE COGGING TORQUE

In the case of segmented-stator PMSMs, the stator laminations are not punched out of the steel at once. On the contrary, each single tooth laminations are punched separately. Therefore, some deviation among the magnetic properties of stator teeth due to the punching effect is inevitable. Furthermore, the stator can be composed of teeth punched by different punching machines or coming from different batches. In this case, the stator is more prone to magnetic asymmetry caused by punching. The deviation among the magnetic properties of the teeth can be caused by difference between the condition of the punching tools like its sharpness and cut clearance [26], which are bound to variation over time owing to wear.

In order to consider the deviation among magnetic properties of the teeth due to punching, one can assign a different a_μ in (1) to each single tooth, as opposed to assuming a single a_μ for the whole stator. It means that the degraded BH curve of the whole stator now is characterized by $a_{\mu i}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 12\}$, which correspond to 12 teeth.

a_μ determines the distance from the cut edge affected by punching. Lower a_μ means smaller degradation depth. Moreover, the profile of degradation is continuous and defined as an exponential function according to (1), which means the highest reduction in permeability occur in the cut edges and the impact diminishes at distances far enough from the cut edges. Therefore, the material BH curve and permeability curves lie between the dashed and solid line in Fig. 9, depending on a_μ and the distance from the cut edge. The dashed curves are obtained with $x = 0$ in (1) and represent the material magnetic properties at the cut edge, while the solid curves shows non-degraded BH curve and permeability of the steel, which are obtained with $x = \infty$ in (1).

As an example, in Fig. 10 (a) and (b), the permeability maps with imposed flux density 1T in all elements with symmetric and non-symmetric stators are shown, respectively.

Fig. 10. Relative permeability distribution map with imposed flux density 1 T in all elements with (a) symmetric (b) asymmetric stator

In the symmetric stator, $a_{\mu i}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 12\}$ are identical and equal to its nominal value in Table IV. It can be seen that the permeability distribution is the same among all teeth. However, within each single teeth, the permeability increases contentiously from its minimum in cut edges to its maximum value in the center of teeth.

On the contrary, with asymmetric stator, $a_{\mu i}$ changes from 1.4mm in tooth 1 to 2.5mm in tooth 12 by 0.1mm step in counterclockwise direction (tooth 1 is assumed to be in the right-hand side of the stator aligned with horizontal axis). In this case, it can be seen that the profile of the permeability increase from the cut edges to the middle of tooth varies among teeth depending on the a_μ ; teeth with smaller a_μ reach higher permeability in the middle of tooth.

In order to study the effect of variation of tooth degradation on the cogging torque, it is assumed that $a_{\mu i}$ $i \in \{1, \dots, 12\}$ are independent, random variables defined by 12 normal distributions with average value of 2mm and standard deviation of 0.333mm. As an example, $a_{\mu 1}$ for 300 stators is shown in Fig. 11 (a). It should be noted that because $a_{\mu i}$ are defined as independent variables, they varies among the tooth of the stator.

The cogging torque of the machine is calculated using FE for these 300 stators. The distribution of the 10th order torque amplitude is shown in Fig. 11 (b). Moreover, the scatter plot

Fig. 11. Statistical analysis of the machine cogging torque for 300 stators; (a) distribution of $a_{\mu 1}$, (b) distribution of 10th order amplitude, (c) scatter plot of 10th order amplitude, (d) scatter plot of 60th order amplitude

of the 10th order torque versus the standard deviation of $a_{\mu i}$ is shown in Fig. 11 (c). It should be noted the standard deviation for each stator is calculated using 12 values for $a_{\mu i}$. Finally, the scatter plot of 60th order torque which is the first harmonic of the inherent cogging torque is shown in Fig. 11 (d). Because the other orders of the cogging torque have relatively small values, they are not shown.

According to Fig. 11 (c), it can be observed that the induced 10th order due to the asymmetry in the stator caused by the variation of the punching parameters can have considerable amplitude compared to the inherent cogging torque shown in Fig. 11 (d). The average cogging torque among these 300 stators is 0.25N.cm. However, the maximum calculated value is 0.86N.cm, which is almost 3 times bigger than inherent cogging torque with average 0.30N.cm.

Furthermore, according to Fig. 11 (c), big $\sigma(a_{\mu i})$ in a stator can lead to higher 10th cogging torque. However, it is not enough condition. It means that there can be stators with relatively big $\sigma(a_{\mu i})$ but small 10th order. Therefore, in addition to the variation of $\sigma(a_{\mu i})$ among stator teeth, the arrangement of teeth with given $a_{\mu i}$ plays a role in the induced cogging torque. This issue will be discussed in detail in the next section. Finally regarding 60th order, it can be observed in Fig. 11 (d) that its value does not change noticeably among 300 stators and is almost equal to its value for the symmetric stator. It shows that at least for the assumed distribution of $a_{\mu i}$, the asymmetry in the stator does not affect the inherent cogging torque considerably.

VI. STATOR TEETH ARRANGEMENT EFFECT

In order to study further the effect of teeth arrangement with given $a_{\mu s}$ on the 10th order torque, it is helpful to calculate the cogging torque analytically based on some simplifying assumptions. When the magnetic saturation of the iron is neglected, the cogging torque can be calculated as the partial derivative of the magnetic energy with respect to rotor position [27]:

$$T(\theta) = -\frac{\partial W}{\partial \theta} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \int_V \frac{B(x, y, z, \theta)^2}{2\mu_0} dv \quad (6)$$

where θ is the rotor position versus stator, W the magnetic energy, and $B(x, y, z, \theta)$ the flux density. The integral is calculated over the volume of the machine. Assuming that

the magnetic energy stored out of the magnetic airgap is negligible, (6) can be simplified as:

$$T(\theta) = -\frac{L_s g R_s}{2\mu_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} \int_0^{2\pi} \Lambda(\theta)^2 F(\zeta - \theta)^2 d\zeta \quad (7)$$

where L_s is the axial length of the stator, g the airgap width, R_s the inner radius of the stator. ζ is the angular position in the airgap in terms of the stator coordinate. $\Lambda(\theta)$ is the airgap permeance function and $F(\zeta - \theta)$ the equivalent magnetomotive force of the rotor magnets.

When the rotor poles are completely identical, the square of $F(\zeta - \theta)$ in (7) in terms of Fourier series can be written as:

$$F(\zeta - \theta)^2 = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} f_n e^{inp(\zeta - \theta)} \quad (8)$$

with p the number of poles and i the imaginary unit.

Neglecting inter-tooth effect in permeance function (it means the permeance function under each tooth is not affected by the other teeth), the square of $\Lambda(\theta)$ in (7) can be written as the sum of squared permeance of each single tooth as:

$$\Lambda(\zeta)^2 = \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \Lambda_j(\zeta)^2 \quad (9)$$

with N_s the number of stator teeth. Again $\Lambda_j(\zeta)^2$ can be written as a Fourier series:

$$\Lambda_j(\zeta)^2 = \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} \lambda_{j,m} e^{im(\zeta + (j-1)\frac{2\pi}{N_s})} \quad (10)$$

Putting (8)–(10) in (7) and calculating the integral, the p^{th} order of cogging torque is calculated as:

$$T_p(\theta) = -\frac{L_s g R_s}{\mu_0} \Re \left(f_1 \left\{ \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \lambda_{j,p} e^{i\frac{2\pi}{N_s} p(j-1)} \right\} e^{-ip\theta} \right) \quad (11)$$

According to the sum in the curly brackets in (11) and based on the aforementioned assumptions, the p^{th} order of cogging torque can be considered as the vector sum of the cogging torques of separate teeth. The vector of cogging torque of a tooth has an amplitude proportional to $\lambda_{j,p}$, while its phase equals $\frac{2\pi}{N_s} p(j-1)$; $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_s\}$.

Fig. 12. Vector diagram of the cogging torque based on contribution of individual teeth; the number next to the vector shows the tooth number (teeth are numbered consecutively in counter-clockwise direction and tooth number 1 is aligned with horizontal axis on the right side of the stator); (a) symmetric stator (b) worst-case stator

It can be assumed that the variation in the punching parameters among teeth slightly changes $\lambda_{j,p}$ around its nominal value for the symmetric stator, i.e. $\lambda_{j,p} = \lambda_p + \Delta\lambda_j$. When a_{μ} in (1) is bigger than its nominal value, the permeance of the tooth decreases and therefore $\Delta\lambda_j$ is negative. By contrast, smaller a_{μ} means higher permeability and positive $\Delta\lambda_j$.

When all the stator teeth are identical, i.e. $\Delta\lambda_j = \Delta\lambda$, the sum in the curly brackets adds up to zero (see the vector diagram in Fig. 12 (a)). However, in the case of asymmetry, the sum can result in different values, depending on the teeth arrangement.

Considering the 10-pole PMSM in this paper, it can be easily shown that the tooth pairs facing each other on the two sides of the stator have the same phase, and therefore their contribution to the cogging torque adds up. On the other hand, the cogging torques of tooth pairs with 90° mechanical phase shift are 180° out of phase and therefore cancel out each other. Thus, it can be shown when the teeth arrangement corresponds to the vector diagram shown in Fig. 12 (b), the highest 10th order torque result. The corresponding tooth arrangement with given $a_{\mu i}$ shown in Fig. 13 (a), which is referred to as the worst-case stator. In this figure, the $a_{\mu i}$ are set to their minimum and maximum values according to the distribution in Fig. 13(a) (1mm and 3mm respectively) for having maximum 10th order. Furthermore, the amplitude of the calculated 10th order for this stator is 1.92 N.cm, which is the maximum possible value for the assumed distribution for $a_{\mu i}$.

In Fig. 13 (b) and (c), the $a_{\mu i}$ maps for two stators selected from the 300 stators in Section V with similar standard deviation but different 10 order torque are shown. The cogging torque over one period for these two stators alongside the worst-case stator is shown in Fig. 14. The stator in Fig. 13 (b) has standard deviation of 0.47mm with 10 order torque 0.800N.cm, while the stator in Fig. 13 (c) has standard deviation 0.42mm and 10th order torque 0.085N.cm. Despite almost equal standard deviation, the cogging torque of the first stator is 10 times bigger than the second one. By comparing the stator with big 10th order torque with the worst case stator, it can be seen the tooth arrangement pattern is similar to the worst-case one. However, in the stator with

low 10th order torque, the tooth arrangement is such that the contribution of different teeth cancels out to some extent.

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the effect of the variation in the punching parameters on the cogging torque of a 10-pole, 12-tooth, segmented-stator PMSM designed for power steering application was investigated using FE. It was shown that the asymmetry in the stator caused by punching can introduce extra 10-multiple orders in the cogging torque with comparable or even bigger amplitude than the inherent cogging torque. It depends on how big the difference among the punching parameters of the teeth is and the teeth arrangement. Therefore, in order to minimize the scraps in the mass production of the PMSMs for applications with strict requirements on the cogging torque, teeth with similar properties regarding to punching should be selected while assembling the stator. In this regard, the teeth should come from a batch produced with the same punching tool.

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Fig. 13. a_{μ_i} map of stators with (a) maximum possible 10th order torque 1.92 N.cm and standard deviation 1 mm (b) high 10th order torque 0.800 N.cm and standard deviation 0.47 mm, and (c) low 10th order torque 0.085 N.cm and standard deviation 0.42 mm

Fig. 14. Cogging torque over one period for the worst-case stator and the two stators with high and low 10th order torque shown in Fig. 13

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